

Secale africanum African rye

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Monocot

Size: Up to 1 m in height

Distribution:

Wild rye grows naturally in moist meadows and streambanks in the Roggeveld - an area on the southern African escarpment margin between Sutherland and Middelpos in the Northern Cape.

Importance:

This is the only rye species from southern Africa. It is palatable and has been used for grazing. It is not known whether it was used as a cereal by the indigenous peoples in the past (pza.sanbi.org/secale-africanum).

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 151.81 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 6.81 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 6.19 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.6% [Single: 92.7%, Duplicated: 5.9%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 779.54 kilobases

Contig number: 24 195

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